

Preliminary Investigation of Target k_{eff} Search for Fuel Feed in MSRs

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ABSTRACT

Fluid fuel molten salt reactor (MSR) concepts may achieve continuous-at-power operation with continuous or batch fresh fuel feed to counter reactivity loss from fuel burnup and fission product buildup. Accurate modeling and simulation of MSRs requires consideration of online fuel feed during depletion as well as a capability to determine the required feed amount to maintain a target multiplication factor (k_{eff}). As a first step supporting a full implementation of a new search capability into the SCALE code system's TRITON reactor physics and depletion sequence, a preliminary investigation was performed to identify the best approach for a critical feed search capability considering computation time and accuracy. Using a simple iterative approach in which initial feed amounts were guessed based on previous depletion steps, the main drivers of computation time were found as the Monte Carlo neutron transport settings and the applied tolerance for the target k_{eff} . In the applied model, with tight convergence criteria (k_{eff} convergence to 8 pcm and a tolerance of ± 15 pcm), the critical search calculation required twice the number of neutron transport calculations compared to a depletion calculation without critical search. In contrast, with a relaxed tolerance of ± 50 pcm, the overall computation time for the critical search for merely increased by 30-40%. Further studies will be performed before implementing the critical search capability into TRITON.

Keywords: molten salt reactor, critical search, depletion, SCALE, TRITON

1. INTRODUCTION

One advantage of fluid fuel molten salt reactors (MSRs) is that they are designed for continuous operation with online refueling, i.e. they can be refueled continuously or in batches without requiring shut down. In theory, fresh fuel can be added to the reactor to adequately offset reactivity losses due to fuel depletion and fission product buildup. Thus, the implementation of an online fuel feed option and a capability to determine the correct fuel feed amount in reactor physics codes is crucial for enabling accurate simulation of actual MSR operation. This is also important for understanding burnup-dependent reactor behavior or any fuel feed requirements for an MSR reactor design.

The TRITON reactor physics sequence within the SCALE code system [1] is used to perform burnup-dependent reactor physics analyses by coupling a 1D, 2D, or 3D geometry neutron transport solver with the ORIGEN depletion code. Recent development efforts have focused on enabling capabilities for accurate fuel inventory prediction in MSRs [2]. Key capabilities are nuclide removal and nuclide feed during depletion: Specific nuclides can be removed from the fuel during depletion by defining

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nuclide-specific removal rates to simulate, for example, noble gas removal through the off-gas system; a continuous feed capability can be used to define the continuous addition of, for example, fresh fuel during depletion as feed rate in units such as grams per second. Ongoing development efforts include a “batch feed” capability which will allow the addition of specific amounts of fresh fuel at specific points in time to the system’s fuel salt. Additionally, a critical feed search capability is planned to automatically calculate the correct fresh fuel feed rate to maintain a target value of k_{eff} .

In this study, a preliminary investigation was performed to identify the best approach for a critical feed search capability considering computation time and accuracy. A simple methodology for a critical search capability using “batch feed” at selected points in time was implemented to gain insights into the time-dependence of the feed amount, the computational burden of this approach, the impact of volume balancing the feed amount, and the linearity of the problem.

2. MODELS AND METHODOLOGY

Performing a critical feed search is an inherently nonlinear problem because the correct fuel composition is not necessarily known before the neutron transport calculation that determines the multiplication factor is performed. To solve similar nonlinear depletion problems, various iterative and inline approaches have been proposed over the years. Iterative depletion algorithms such as [3, 4, 5] have previously been developed for ameliorating convergence issues related to thermal hydraulics and xenon oscillations during depletion. Iterative methods for criticality search, unrelated to depletion, have also been proposed and previously used for control rod [6] and control drum [7] criticality searches. Results from these studies indicate that secant-like methods perform reasonably well for criticality searches although multiple neutron transport solutions may sometimes be required if the initial guess is poor. Inline depletion algorithms, such as those in [8, 9, 10], have traditionally been used for controlling equilibrium xenon. They generally offer the advantage of being able to solve a nonlinear problem in a single neutron transport step although their implementation is usually more difficult compared to an iterative method. Though the inline algorithms only require a single neutron transport step, a current review of the state of the art suggests that an iterative approach with multiple neutron transport iterations is still acceptable.

2.1. Depletion Algorithm and Wrapper

Under the existing TRITON implementation, a deterministic or a Monte Carlo neutron transport code is internally coupled with the ORIGEN depletion solver via a predictor–corrector algorithm. To avoid interfering with the existing implementation and for the purpose of enabling quick testing of potential methods for determining a criticality search, a script-based coupling of TRITON and ORIGEN was developed. The intention is to fully implement an iterative or inline critical batch feed search method using the findings of this work in a future SCALE release.

The coupling is achieved using a simple Python module, to couple a Monte Carlo neutron transport solver under TRITON with ORIGEN. In this case, the Monte Carlo neutron transport code KENO-VI with multigroup cross sections was selected. The TRITON sequence automatically computes relevant tallies over the depletion mixtures of interest with the selected neutron transport code. ORIGEN then performs the depletion calculations for each depletion mixture using mixture-specific fluxes and 1-group cross sections from TRITON. The algorithm, shown below as Algorithm 1, uses a first-order explicit Euler formulation to couple neutron transport with time-dependent depletion, where the neutron transport operator is represented by ψ , the nuclide number density at step n is represented by N_n , and the transition matrix is represented by A_n . Algorithm 1 can be adjusted to consider the batch feed of a predefined feed mixture composition, N_{feed} , prior to each neutron transport pass, with the goal of achieving a target k_{eff} . Without describing the steps to guess or determine the proper feed amount, the new algorithm is described in Algorithm 2, where $F(\theta(t))$ is the function that determines the batch feed

multiplier, m , based on variables described by $\theta_n(t)$. $\theta_n(t)$ is a relatively arbitrary function (might for example be a function of xenon concentration history, burnup, previous feed guesses, and neutron flux, among other factors). The variable m is a simple scalar variable that determines the feed amount that enters the mixture; it can essentially be interpreted as the volume fraction of each mixture.

Algorithm 1: Explicit Euler depletion

Input: $N_0, \Delta t, n_{\text{steps}}$
for $n = 0, \dots, n_{\text{steps}}$ **do**
 $A_n \leftarrow \psi(N_n)$
 $N_{n+1} \leftarrow N_n \exp(A_n \Delta t_n)$
end

Algorithm 2: Explicit Euler depletion with feed search

Input: $N_0, \Delta t, n_{\text{steps}}, N_{\text{feed}}, t_{\text{feed}}, \epsilon, k_{\text{target}}$
for $n = 0, \dots, n_{\text{steps}}$ **do**
 if $t_n \in t_{\text{feed}}$ **then**
 while $|k_{\text{eff}} - k_{\text{target}}| > \epsilon$ **do**
 $m \leftarrow F(\theta_n(t))$
 $N_n \leftarrow (1 - m)N_n + mN_{\text{feed}}$
 $A_n, k_{\text{eff}} \leftarrow \psi(N_n)$
 end
 end
 else
 $A_n, k_{\text{eff}} \leftarrow \psi(N_n)$
 end
 $N_{n+1} \leftarrow N_n \exp(A_n \Delta t_n)$
end

2.2. Method of Determining Batch Feed Amounts

Without considering inline methods (e.g., those from [9, 10, 11]) in this specific work, it is assumed that an iterative strategy with multiple neutron transport calculations will be necessary if the initial feed guess is poor and k_{target} is not achieved within the first iteration. A secant method based on [6] is used in place of $F(\theta(t))$ to iterate on the batch feed multiplier, m , until the problem eigenvalue falls within ϵ of k_{target} . Underrelaxation determined by ϵ is optional. The next guess for the feed multiplier, m_n , is calculated based on Eq. 1 and Eq. 2.

With an iterative method, multiple neutron transport calculations might be required during some depletion steps; it is therefore important to understand and analyze the time-dependent feed behavior during depletion in this preliminary work so that a better method can be developed that reduces calculation time in future implementations.

$$\left(\frac{dk}{dm}\right)_n = \frac{k_{n,\text{new}} - k_{n,\text{old}}}{m_{n,\text{new}} - m_{n,\text{old}}} \quad (1)$$

$$m_n = m_{n,\text{new}} + \frac{\epsilon(k_{\text{target}} - k_{n,\text{new}})}{(dk/dm)_n} \quad (2)$$

2.3. Volume Conservation During Feed

Volume conservation during any type of MSR feed calculation is highly important, because the reactor core is assumed to contain a fixed fuel volume, whereas the addition of a fresh fuel feed implies a variable total volume of the fuel salt. It is assumed that during actual operation the additional fuel volume is causing the salt level in certain components in the loop to rise. In TRITON simulations, fuel salt can be added such that the volume of the core is kept constant, while the volume in the entire system is considered variable.

The volume balancing strategy is briefly considered here in the context of adding fuel into the reactor. Two strategies for volume balancing with a batch feed scenario could be considered. In the first strategy, fuel salt is added to the reactor, resulting in the total fuel volume being greater than the real volume of the reactor. Then, the overflow volume is computed, the number densities of the feed and fuel salt are smeared, and the volume is reduced based on the new density of the fuel salt. This approach effectively smears the number densities across the feed and fuel mixtures and then drains the reactor to conserve volume. In the second strategy, a fraction of the fuel salt is first drained, and then feed salt is added to fill the empty volume. The difference between the two strategies is that a given amount of the feed salt is drained in the first strategy, whereas all the feed salt is retained in the reactor in the second strategy. For the purposes of computing and reporting feed amounts in this work, the first strategy is chosen when reporting and discussing the feed amount.

2.4. Application Example

The molten salt breeder reactor (MSBR) was a graphite-moderated thermal spectrum liquid salt reactor design originally developed for breeding purposes using a thorium fuel cycle. The model used in this study, shown in Figure 1, consists of a simple representative 2D unit cell from the MSBR geometry, and the fuel is 60-30-10 mol% LiF-BeF₂-UF₄ at 2.3 wt% ²³⁵U enrichment and 99.995 wt% ⁷Li enrichment. The MSBR unit cell geometry and material description are taken from the full MSBR model geometry used for similar MSR feed-related depletion studies performed with SCALE [12].

The neutron transport solver under TRITON that was selected in this study is the KENO-VI Monte Carlo code used with SCALE's 252-group multigroup library. The Monte Carlo calculations were performed with 250,000 neutron histories per generation, 390 active generations, and 10 skipped generations. This resulted in a 1 σ standard deviation of approximately 8 pcm for the effective multiplication factor.

Figure 1. 2D MSBR unit cell used in this study.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Verification of the Explicit Euler Scheme

First, the script-based explicit Euler scheme that couples TRITON and ORIGEN was verified. The test problem considered depletion without any feed for a single year, using time steps of 10 days, with smaller time steps at the beginning of life. The problem was ran twice and then compared—once using TRITON and once using the script-based explicit Euler scheme. The end of life (EOL) percent differences between the native TRITON implementation and the script-based explicit Euler scheme, for the ²³⁵U, ²³⁹Pu, and ¹³⁵Xe nuclide densities, were found to be 0.48%, -0.89%, and -0.89%, respectively. Time steps of 10 days are also sufficient to model the problem of interest in the explicit Euler scheme.

3.2. Feed Search With and Without Realistic Fission Product Treatment

Two different cases were run with fresh fuel feed: one with and one without the removal of certain fission products (xenon, krypton, and noble metals). In each case, the value of k_{target} was arbitrarily set to be 1.120 with a tolerance of $\epsilon = \pm 15$ pcm. Additionally, the value of ϵ was chosen to be relatively small because k_{eff} was found to be relatively insensitive to the feed amount at EOL; this value is also approximately twice the 1σ uncertainty of k_{eff} . Eigenvalue results are shown in Figure 2 for each case. The feed amount to maintain k_{target} is also shown in Figure 3 along with the variation with time of number densities for selected nuclides.

The batch feed amount for the case without any xenon or noble metal removal shows an unexpectedly variable trend. The amount of feed needed to maintain the target eigenvalue initially increases and eventually saturates at about 120 g of feed every 10 days. For the case with fission product removal, the feed amount is relatively constant in time except for some very small fluctuations due to statistical noise. The results indicate that blending the feed mixture with depleted fuel while conserving volume causes a significant amount of depleted fuel to be removed from the problem. For example, Figure 3 shows the ^{239}Pu and ^{135}Xe concentrations in the problems with feed to be much lower than in the problem without feed due to this volume conservation. This implies that the xenon penalty and any reactivity gained from plutonium production will be reduced.

Additionally, when removing xenon and noble metals, the amount of feed required to maintain the target eigenvalue is noticeably reduced when compared to the case without xenon and noble metal removal, in this case by approximately 66%. When removing fission products, the feed amount is also relatively constant in time after 140 days—approximately 50 days after feed is first added.

For this work, the initial guess for the feed amount was made off of a simple linear extrapolation of the feed from the two previous timesteps. If this was insufficient and k_{target} was not achieved, the derivative in Eq. 1 was approximated by perturbing the feed amount by 20% and performing a second neutron transport simulation. With an approximation for the derivative, the secant method from Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 was used to iterate and update the feed guess.

For the problem without fission product removal, 66 neutron transport simulations were required for the 35 timesteps where feed was required. For the second problem with fission product removal, 59 transport simulations were required for the 27 timesteps where feed was required. As many as six transport steps were required for some timesteps in each of the problems. Overall, the computation time for a depletion calculation with critical feed search required about twice as many neutron transport calculations as a depletion calculation without feed search. The computational effort could be greatly reduced by increasing the k_{target} tolerance ϵ . For example, it was found that increasing ϵ from 15 pcm to 50 pcm caused a reduction of the number of neutron transport simulations from 66 to 48 and from 59 to 36, for the problems without and with fission product removal, respectively, i.e. only a 30-40% increase in computation time compared to a depletion calculation without feed search.

3.3. Feed Sensitivity with Burnup

Assessing the eigenvalue sensitivity to feed and its variation as a function of burnup is important, as it was shown in the previous section that the feed amount necessary to maintain a critical eigenvalue is nonconstant. The variation in eigenvalue sensitivity to feed may occur for a variety of reasons, including xenon being displaced and removed from the core when adding feed salt, plutonium production leading to less reliance on uranium for fission, and the fact that the feed of fresh fuel into the reactor dilutes/replaces the existing concentration of nuclides.

Branch calculations were run for each depletion time step after 10 days, where 40 and 60 g were fed into the EOL concentration from the previous time step. The sensitivity to feed, dk_{eff}/dM , where M is the feed mass in grams, was then computed for the case without fission product removal and is shown

Figure 2. k_{eff} as a function of time for the cases with and without fission product removal.

Figure 3. Feed required to maintain k_{target} (top left), ^{235}U number density (top right), ^{239}Pu number density (bottom left), and ^{135}Xe number density (bottom right). In the top left graph, the lines represent the cumulative feed and the markers represent the feed amount.

in Figure 4. Next, branch calculations were also performed where the feed amount was varied from 10 to 300 g at select points in time; the results of these calculations are also shown in Figure 4. Figure 4 indicates that the k_{eff} sensitivity to feed is mostly constant with time and nearly linear as a function of the feed amount at each given point in time, especially in the vicinity of k_{target} . For an iterative approach, this essentially means that if a poor initial guess is made for the fuel feed, and a second guess is made such that $(dk/dm)_n$ from Eq. 1 can be approximated, then a secant or similar method for finding the

feed amount should converge quickly.

Figure 4. Sensitivity of eigenvalue to feed rate as a function of time (left) and k_{eff} as a function of feed (right) in the problem with feed and no fission product removal.

The value of dk_{eff}/dM is shown in Figure 4 (left) to be mostly constant with time, with the average value being 14.4 pcm per gram. Also, the statistical eigenvalue uncertainty in these calculations was low—usually 7–8 pcm, which is well within the standard acceptable range when performing Monte Carlo eigenvalue simulations. However, even with a fairly low eigenvalue uncertainty, the relative uncertainty when computing the derivative dk_{eff}/dM remains high which might affect convergence if ϵ is reduced. Dividing the k_{eff} search tolerance, ϵ , by the sensitivity, dk_{eff}/dM , reveals how tightly the feed amount in grams needs to be converged at each timestep. For the problem without fission product removal, this tolerance was 1.04 grams—or roughly 0.85% of the average feed amount considering time steps past 70 days.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A preliminary investigation was performed to inform the best approach for a planned critical feed search capability in the TRITON reactor physics sequence of the SCALE code system considering computation time and accuracy. A simple methodology for a critical search capability was used to gain insights into the time-dependence of the feed amount, the computational burden of this approach, the impact of volume balancing the feed amount, and the linearity of the problem.

The simple critical search capability was applied to depletion calculations of a test MSR model with and without fission product removal were performed. The following observations will be used to inform the final implementation into the TRITON sequence:

- The fuel feed required to reach k_{target} differed significantly between a model with and a model without fission product removal (i.e., Xe removal). Without any fission product removal, the feed amount required to reach k_{target} increased linearly from 10 to 70 days. Afterwards, the feed amount required to maintain k_{target} was constant at approximately 120 grams. For the problem with fission product removal, the feed required was nearly constant with approximately 40 grams of fresh fuel feed needed every 10 days to maintain k_{target} .
- Within a timestep, the variation with of k_{eff} with the batch feed amount was found to be nearly linear. This means that once an approximation for the derivative of k_{eff} with respect to feed is made, the feed amount can be converged quickly, requiring few neutron transport calculations. If an iterative secant-like method is eventually implemented within TRITON, this means that similar problems to the ones tested here will likely not require much—if any—relaxation.
- The Monte Carlo neutron transport settings and the tolerance on k_{target} drive the computation

time. For this study, the 1σ standard deviation on k_{eff} was approximately 8 pcm and the tolerance on k_{eff} for the feed search was 15 pcm. These settings resulted in approximately twice the computational effort to solve the critical search problem compared to the corresponding depletion calculation without critical search. If ϵ was instead increased to 50 pcm, the computation time would only increase by 30 to 40% compared to the problem without critical search.

Further testing is planned to study the impact of the time stepping, to develop guidance on tolerances ϵ for the critical search in comparison to the k_{eff} 1σ statistical uncertainty, and to extend the testing to depletion calculations beyond 1 year to cover full MSR operation times. The goal is to implement a critical search capability in TRITON that provides accurate solutions within reasonable tolerances within feasible computational costs.

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